

3,082 document results

(TITLE-ABS-

KEY ((laminectomy OR diskectom* OR discectom* OR (surg* W/3 decompression*) OR (spin* W/3 fusion*)) OR ((neurosurg* OR orthop?edic* OR (spin* W/3 surg*)) AND ((back W/3 pain) OR (low W/3 back W/3 pain) OR radicul* OR (spin* W/3 disease*) OR (spine* W/3 column*) OR (lumbar W/3 vertebra*))) OR ((spine* OR spinal* OR lumbar*) W/7 (surg* OR neurosurg* OR orthop?ed*)))) AND ((TITLE-ABS-KEY (telemedicine* OR telehealth* OR telehealth* OR telephone* OR (cell* W/3 phone*) OR (mobile W/3 phone*) OR smartphone* OR smartphone* OR tablet* OR (mobile W/3 application*) OR (tele W/3 rehabilitation*) OR telenurs* OR videoconf* OR (video W/3 conf*) OR (health W/3 communica*) OR (medic* W/3 inform*) OR (inform* W/3 communicat* W/3 techn*) OR (inform* W/3 application*) OR (nurs* W/3 inform*) OR (health W/3 inform* W/3 tech*) OR (((electr onic W/3 health W/3 service*) OR ehealth OR ehealth) W/5 (communicat*)))) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY (((home W/3 visit*) OR (house W/3 call*) OR (real-time W/3 support*) OR (after W/3 car*) OR aftercar* OR aftercar* OR (followup W/3 car*) OR (follow-up W/3 car*) OR (followup W/3 support*) OR (follow-up W/3 support*) OR (remote W/3 monitor*) OR (active W/3 post-discharg* W/3 surveillanc*) OR simulation* OR (instruction* W/3 film*) OR (instruction* W/3 video*) OR analgesia* OR (pain W/3 manag*) OR (clinic* W/3 teach* W/3 method*) OR (patient* W/3 discharg* W/3 educat*) OR (patient* W/3

educat*) OR (patient* W/3 car*)))) OR (TITLE-ABS-
 KEY ((self-
 car* OR (self W/3 car*) OR (health W/3 promot*) OR (mul-
 ti-disciplin* W/3 car*) OR (multidisciplin* W/3 car*) OR self-
 manag* OR (self W/3 manag*) OR (home W/3 rehabilitation
 *) OR recover* OR convalescence* OR rehab* OR (mobile W
 /3 team\$) OR (text W/3 messag*) OR (pre-
 operative W/3 educat*) OR (preoperative W/3 educat*) OR
 (preoperative W/3 exercise*) OR (pre-
 operative W/3 exercise*) OR prehabilitation* OR (emotional
 W/3 adjust*) OR (adaptive W/3 behav*) OR (psychologic*
 W/3 adjust*) OR (adapt* W/3 psychologic*) OR (physiologic
 * W/3 adjust*) OR (adapt* W/3 physiologic*))))) AND (TIT
 LE-ABS-
 KEY (((short W/3 time W/3 stay*) OR (short W/3 term W/3
 stay*) OR (short W/3 time W/3 hospitalization*) OR (short
 W/3 term W/3 hospitalization AND *) OR (return* W/3 ho
 me*) OR (hospital* W/3 home*) OR discharg* OR postdisch
 arg* OR (post W/3 discharg*) OR post-
 discharg* OR (transition* W/3 home*) OR (length* W/3 sta
 y*))))